

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVING THE POSITION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE E-PARTICIPATION INDEX AND ONLINE SERVICE INDEX: ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE AND SUGGESTIONS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the foreign experience and considers different strategies to improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the E-Participation Index and Online Service Index. Furthermore, in this study, there are various recommendations for improving the situation in the country according to various sub-indicators of the both indices.

Keywords: Electronic Participation Index, E-information Indicator, E-consultation indicator, Online Services Index

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tajriba tahlil qilinadi va O'zbekiston Respublikasining Elektron ishtirok indeksi va Onlayn xizmat ko'rsatish indeksidagi o'rnini yaxshilash bo'yicha turli strategiyalar ko'rib chiqiladi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu tadqiqotda har ikkala indeksning turli kichik ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha mamlakatdagi vaziyatni yaxshilash bo'yicha turli tavsiyalar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: Elektron ishtirok indeksi, Elektron ma'lumot ko'rsatkichi, Elektron maslahat ko'rsatkichi, Onlayn xizmatlar indeksi

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется зарубежный опыт и рассматриваются различные стратегии по улучшению позиций Республики Узбекистан в Индексе электронного участия и Индексе онлайн-услуг. Кроме того, в данном исследовании имеются различные рекомендации по улучшению ситуации в стране по различным субпоказателям обоих индексов.

Ключевые слова: Индекс электронного участия, Индикатор электронной информации, Индикатор электронных консультаций, Индекс онлайн-услуг

Introduction

E-participation refers to the involvement of individuals and communities in the policy-making process through the utilization of information and communication technologies (ICTs). Uzbekistan needs to consider modifying its large spectrum of IT infrastructure such as internet network speed, fixed broadband services and institutional framework as well as content creation to improve its role in E-participation rankings. Online Service Index is a measurement of a government's ability and willingness to offer services and engage with its citizens through electronic means. It assesses the extent to which a government provides online platforms and tools to facilitate the delivery of services, as well as their accessibility and user-friendliness. When it comes to this index, the country is seeking to ameliorate its human resources potential with involving more IT specialists to teach software developers, cybersecurity specialists and data analysts.

E-Participation Index

E-Participation Index was included as an additional index to the United Nations E-Government Survey. This index has three main parts:

- E-information: Providing public information to citizens and ensuring participation by having access to information without demand or on demand;
- E-consultation: Engaging citizens to discuss and contribute public policies and services;
- E-decision-making is the extension of citizens' liberties by co-making political decisions and co-producing the components of public services and their delivery methods.

Japan is the leading country in the world in E-participation index. Achieving this result can be attributed to Japan's IT strategy at the beginning of the 21st century. It is based on the "knowledge-oriented society". The country aims to create an environment in which the market-based private sector can realize its full potential and make Japan the most advanced IT country in the world within five years through the following measures:

- 1) Building a high-speed Internet network and providing constant internet access.
- 2) Establishing the rules of e-commerce, laying the foundation for its development
- 3) Establishment of E-government
- 4) Cultivating high-quality human resources for the new era.

Aforementioned, in the strategy of building a "knowledge-based society", factors such as the importance of the IT revolution, the increase in demand for new infrastructure, similar strategies of other countries, and the need for the development of a national strategy were of great importance. Certainly, the first step in implementing such a strategy is to build an information-literate society that can share its wealth of knowledge without geographic, physical, or economic barriers. The second step is to carry out reforms that will create a diversified and efficient economic system based on free and fair competition. The third step is to attract knowledge and talent from around the world, and to gather and disseminate the most advanced information and technology, and to contribute to the development of a "knowledge-based society" on a global scale.

The private sector should play a leading role in creating network infrastructure. The government, in turn, should support free and fair competition and create an environment that allows the private sector to fully utilize its potential. The government should also enact competition laws based on the philosophy of "promoting consumer benefits" and "encouraging healthy competition".

In order to improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to the e-participation index, it is necessary to consider the following initiatives and proposals:

- Based on Japan's strategy, the following conditions must be ensured when building an Ultra High Speed Internet network: Available anytime, anywhere and for everyone; Variety of services and a wide choice of them; Secure, easy and reliable; Inexpensive, high-speed and efficient internet transmission; The same quality and world-standard network regardless of geographical location.
- Implementation of the provision of virtual existence of public and private companies in improving online services: user-friendly websites, active pages on social networks, responsive e-mail system.
- Analysis of foreign practice on crowdsourcing and introduction of its appropriate features in Uzbekistan.
- Increasing the digital literacy of the population by creating online information databases, regarding special offline and online activities.

- Helping the population by reducing mobile internet prices in order to improve the quality of using digital services. Therefore, allocating subsidies to mobile operators to reduce tariff costs.
- Establishing the provision of digital devices to the segment of the population that does not have such devices. In order to fulfill it, it is necessary to establish the sale of mobile devices and other gadgets at low prices through interest-free payment plans.

E-information indicator

In order to increase the ease of obtaining electronic information, it is necessary to pay great attention to the electronic presence of all types of enterprises, organizations, in particular, private organizations. Ensuring the reliability, speed and accuracy of electronic information will be massively impactful. Ensuring transparency of electronic coverage of many government decision-making processes might play a key role in this process. For this reason, the grounds for the adoption of various laws, decisions and decrees should be presented to citizens electronically, electronic information centers should be established, and any information should be provided if requested by citizens.

Initiatives and proposals to improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to E-information indicator:

- Creating various educational programs to improve Internet literacy.
- Organization of online classes on Vlogging for foreign audiences.
- Organization of promotional activities through the mass media in connection with the popularization of electronic information among the citizens of the republic (video clips).
- Providing online master classes on conducting internet advertising activities in the national internet segment of the country.
- Development of measures to improve the culture of the population using the Internet.
- In order to develop video blogging on YouTube and Facebook, conduct negotiations with company officials to ensure that the monetization of these social networks works in Uzbekistan.

E-consultation indicator

For the purpose of involving citizens in discussing and contributing to public policies and services, it would be appropriate to make extensive use of foreign experience, in particular, the practice of crowdsourcing in the United Arab Emirates. Crowdsourcing is widely used in public projects of the United Arab Emirates. In particular, in 2019, a tender was announced for a logo that would emphasize the uniqueness of the UAE and strengthen its long-standing positive image to the world. 49 citizens will present their designs. Citizens were asked to choose a logo that would best represent the UAE for the next 50 years. A logo called “7 lines” will be the winner of the open crowdsourcing.

The UAE believes that among the youth there are potential philosophers, artists, writers, entrepreneurs, artisans, strategists and many other talents and considers the youth as the country's human capital. A crowdsourcing platform (<https://crowdsourcing.dct.gov.ae/>) has been launched under the Abu Dhabi Department of Culture and Tourism, through which citizens can participate in various online tests that require innovative talent, creativity and knowledge. Such crowdsourcing events can help improve e-consultation indicator of a country.

Initiatives and proposals to improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to E-consultation indicator:

- Implementation of crowdsourcing practices regarding the e-consultation index. It would be appropriate to discuss state-level projects.

- Launching a nationwide projects digital platform for crowdsourcing. Through this platform, it is possible to organize a dialogue with population and receive electronic advice from the people.

- In order to improve the quality of e-government services, organizing various surveys among the population and ensuring that their results are published online at the end of each year will be crucially important.

Online Service Index

Denmark is ranked 1st in the Online Service Index. Many believe that Denmark achieved this result through its digital strategy. The country's digital strategy promotes the following goals:

1. Lifelong learning: "Denmark needs to become a world leader in providing its citizens with access to modern sciences through digital technologies";

2. E-governance: "Denmark must become a leader in delivering public services to citizens in the most efficient way possible through digital government";

3. Danish Internet Initiatives: "Ensuring citizen participation in transparent political decision-making through fast Internet services".

In Denmark, "Digital Mail" was established for the exchange of letters between the state and citizens. In this case, the letters will have official and legal force. Access to such mail is through a unique identification number, in which the state communicates with citizens and business owners.

Initiatives and proposals to improve the position of the Republic of Uzbekistan according to Online Service Index:

- Using the experience of foreign countries, in particular, the experience of South Korea and Estonia, to ensure that the Republic of Uzbekistan enters the ranks of the first 30 countries in the index of local online services. For example, according to the experience of Estonia, public services are almost 100% digitized. Interestingly enough, residents can use services without leaving their homes. Very few citizens actually go to public service centers to get their job done. Moreover, people in Estonia buy and sell cars electronically. This is done through the portal of public services, and the buyer transfers the payment amount to the seller's account number, bank card or online wallet. The seller, in turn, enters his personal account using a single key and confirms that his car will be transferred to the name of the buyer. In this case, there is no need for notary services.

- To invite qualified specialists from the countries that are in the leading position in the Online Service Index. The following countries are in the top 10: Denmark, Finland, South Korea, New Zealand, Iceland, Sweden, Australia, Estonia, the Netherlands, USA.

Conclusion

As a conclusion, Uzbekistan can use leading foreign experience to strengthen its positions in E-participation Index (as well as its sub-indicators) and Online Service index. With regards to online services, the country can fully digitize its public services as in Estonia in the long term. On other hand, Uzbekistan must take best lessons from Denmark's and Japan's digital strategies where lifelong learning and knowledge-emergent societies are key goals to promote, respectively. Efforts to engage population in public projects and initiating new crowdsourcing platform for citizens

participation such as in UAE's crowdsourcing experience could enhance the position of the country concerning E-consultation indicator.

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